

Supplementary information

1 Deriving Fisher information matrix

Let a N -sample $\mathbf{Y} = (Y_1, \dots, Y_N)$ following the statistical model :

$$Y_i = \mu + \beta x_i + Z_i \quad (1)$$

where the vector $\mathbf{Z} = (Z_1, \dots, Z_N)$ follows a Gaussian Random Field (GRF) with density f on \mathbb{R}^N :

$$f(\mathbf{z}) = (\det(2\pi\Sigma))^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{z}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{z}}$$

Σ is the covariance matrix of the GRF such that:

$$\Sigma_{ij} = \sigma^2 c\left(\frac{d_{ij}}{a_s}\right)$$

with d_{ij} the euclidean distance between points i and j , σ^2 the variance of observation at each point, $c(\cdot)$ a correlation function which decreases from 1 to 0 over \mathbb{R}^+ and a_s a scaling factor. We note $\tilde{\Sigma}$ the correlation matrix associated to covariance matrix Σ

The log-likelihood of parameters is:

$$l(\mu, \beta, \sigma^2, a_s | \mathbf{z}) = -\frac{1}{2} (N \log(2\pi) + \log(\det \Sigma) + (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x})' \Sigma^{-1} (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x}))$$

Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial l}{\partial \mu} &= \mathbf{1}' \Sigma^{-1} (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x}) \\ \frac{\partial l}{\partial \beta} &= \mathbf{x}' \Sigma^{-1} (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x}) \\ \frac{\partial l}{\partial \sigma^2} &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\det \Sigma} \frac{\partial \det \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2} + (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x})' \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \sigma^2} (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x}) \right) \\ \frac{\partial l}{\partial a_s} &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\det \Sigma} \frac{\partial \det \Sigma}{\partial a_s} + (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x})' \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial a_s} (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x}) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Recalling Jacobi's formula :

$$\frac{\partial \det A}{\partial \theta} = (\det A) \operatorname{tr} \left(A^{-1} \frac{\partial A}{\partial \theta} \right)$$

one obtains that:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial l}{\partial \mu} &= \mathbf{1}' \Sigma^{-1} (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x}) \\ \frac{\partial l}{\partial \beta} &= \mathbf{x}' \Sigma^{-1} (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x}) \\ \frac{\partial l}{\partial \sigma^2} &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2}) + (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x})' \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \sigma^2} (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x}) \right) \\ \frac{\partial l}{\partial a_s} &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\operatorname{tr}(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s}) + (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x})' \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial a_s} (\mathbf{y} - \mu\mathbf{1} - \beta\mathbf{x}) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Then one can derive second order derivatives:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial \mu)^2} &= -\mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{1} \\
 \frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \mu \partial \beta} &= -\mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{x} \\
 \frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \mu \partial \sigma^2} &= \mathbf{1}' \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \sigma^2} (\mathbf{y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x}) \\
 \frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \mu \partial a_s} &= \mathbf{1}' \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial a_s} (\mathbf{y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x}) \\
 \frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial \beta)^2} &= -\mathbf{x}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{x} \\
 \frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \beta \partial \sigma^2} &= \mathbf{x}' \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \sigma^2} (\mathbf{y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x}) \\
 \frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \beta \partial a_s} &= \mathbf{x}' \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial a_s} (\mathbf{y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x}) \\
 \frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial \sigma^2)^2} &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \sigma^2} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2} + \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma}{(\partial \sigma^2)^2} \right) + (\mathbf{y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x})' \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma^{-1}}{(\partial \sigma^2)^2} (\mathbf{y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x}) \right) \\
 \frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \sigma^2 \partial a_s} &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial a_s} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2} + \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2 \partial a_s} \right) + (\mathbf{y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x})' \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \sigma^2 \partial a_s} (\mathbf{y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x}) \right) \\
 \frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial a_s)^2} &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial a_s} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} + \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma}{(\partial a_s)^2} \right) + (\mathbf{y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x})' \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma^{-1}}{(\partial a_s)^2} (\mathbf{y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x}) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Taking probabilistic expectation of these second derivatives over the random variable \mathbf{Y} at true parameters and using that:

$$\mathbb{E}[(\mathbf{Y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x})' A (\mathbf{Y} - \mu \mathbf{1} - \beta \mathbf{x})] = \text{tr}(\Sigma A)$$

one obtains that:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial \mu)^2} \right] &= -\mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{1} \\
 \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \mu \partial \beta} \right] &= -\mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{x} \\
 \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \mu \partial \sigma^2} \right] &= 0 \\
 \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \mu \partial a_s} \right] &= 0 \\
 \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial \beta)^2} \right] &= -\mathbf{x}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{x} \\
 \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \beta \partial \sigma^2} \right] &= 0 \\
 \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \beta \partial a_s} \right] &= 0 \\
 \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial \sigma^2)^2} \right] &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \sigma^2} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2} + \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma}{(\partial \sigma^2)^2} + \Sigma \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma^{-1}}{(\partial \sigma^2)^2} \right) \right) \\
 \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \sigma^2 \partial a_s} \right] &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial a_s} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2} + \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2 \partial a_s} + \Sigma \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \sigma^2 \partial a_s} \right) \right) \\
 \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial a_s)^2} \right] &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(\text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial a_s} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} + \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma}{(\partial a_s)^2} + \Sigma \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma^{-1}}{(\partial a_s)^2} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Noting that:

$$0 = \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1} \Sigma}{\partial \theta_1} = \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \theta_1} \Sigma + \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \theta_1}$$

and that :

$$0 = \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma^{-1} \Sigma}{\partial \theta_1 \partial \theta_2} = \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \theta_1 \partial \theta_2} \Sigma + \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \theta_1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \theta_2} + \frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \theta_2} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \theta_1} + \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial^2 \Sigma}{\partial \theta_1 \partial \theta_2}$$

the three last second order derivatives can be simplified into:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial \sigma^2)^2} \right] &= \frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \sigma^2} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2} \right) = -\frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2} \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2} \right) \\ \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \sigma^2 \partial a_s} \right] &= \frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial \sigma^2} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) = -\frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2} \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) \\ \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial a_s)^2} \right] &= \frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma^{-1}}{\partial a_s} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) = -\frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right)\end{aligned}$$

Further using that:

$$\frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial \sigma^2} = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \Sigma$$

one obtains that :

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial \sigma^2)^2} \right] &= -\frac{N}{2\sigma^4} \\ \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{\partial \sigma^2 \partial a_s} \right] &= -\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) = -\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \right) \\ \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 l}{(\partial a_s)^2} \right] &= -\frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) = -\frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \right)\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the Fisher information matrix of model (1) is:

$$\mathcal{I}(\mu, \beta, \sigma^2, a_s) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{1} & \mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{x} & 0 & 0 \\ \mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{x} & \mathbf{x}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{x} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{N}{2\sigma^4} & \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \right) \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \right) & \frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \right) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Problem 1: mean versus autocorrelation range estimation

Recall the statistical model associated to problem 1:

$$Y_i = \mu + Z_i$$

which is a simplification of model (1), obtained by taking $\beta = 0$. The associated Fisher matrix can be directly derived from (2) as:

$$\mathcal{I}(\mu, \sigma^2, a_s) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{N}{2\sigma^4} & \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \right) \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \right) & \frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \right) \end{pmatrix}$$

Changing parameters μ to exponential parameters $\nu = e^\mu$ and defining the vector of parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\nu, \sigma^2, a_s)$ yields the Fisher information matrix :

$$\mathcal{I}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\nu^2} \mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{N}{2\sigma^4} & \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \right) \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \right) & \frac{1}{2} \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \right) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

From the Fisher information matrix, one can derive the expected mean squared errors associated to $\hat{\nu}$ and \hat{a}_s , denoted $\text{MSE}(\nu)$ and $\text{MSE}(a_s)$ respectively:

$$\text{MSE}(\nu) = \nu^2 \sigma^2 \frac{1}{\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{1}}$$

$$\text{MSE}(a_s) = \frac{2}{\text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s}) - \frac{1}{N} \text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s}) \text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s})}$$

where we used $\Sigma = \sigma^2 \tilde{\Sigma}$. Using above expression, the derivation of corresponding RRMSEs is straightforward.

Problem 2: slope of environmental effect versus autocorrelation range estimation

Recall the statistical model associated to problem 2:

$$Y_i = \tilde{\mu} + \beta \tilde{x}_i + Z_i$$

which is identical to model (1) up to notational changes. The Fisher matrix of this model is thus directly obtained from (2):

$$\mathcal{I}(\tilde{\mu}, \beta, \sigma^2, a_s) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{1} & \mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}} & 0 & 0 \\ \mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}} & \tilde{\mathbf{x}}'\Sigma^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{N}{2\sigma^4} & \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s}) \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s}) & \frac{1}{2} \text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s}) \end{pmatrix}$$

Changing parameters β to exponential parameters $\gamma = e^\beta$ and defining the vector of parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\tilde{\mu}, \gamma, \sigma^2, a_s)$ yields the Fisher information matrix :

$$\mathcal{I}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\mathbf{1} & \frac{1}{\gamma} \mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\gamma} \mathbf{1}'\Sigma^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}} & \frac{1}{\gamma^2} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}'\Sigma^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{N}{2\sigma^4} & \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s}) \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s}) & \frac{1}{2} \text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

From the Fisher information matrix, one can derive the expected mean squared errors associated to $\hat{\gamma}$ and \hat{a}_s , denoted $\text{MSE}(\gamma)$ and $\text{MSE}(a_s)$ respectively:

$$\text{MSE}(\gamma) = \gamma^2 \sigma^2 \frac{\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{1}}{(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}})(\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{1}) - (\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}})^2}$$

$$\text{MSE}(a_s) = \frac{2}{\text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} \tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s}) - \frac{1}{N} \text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s}) \text{tr}(\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s})}$$

Using above expression, the derivation of corresponding RRMSEs is straightforward.

2 Asymptotic errors when $a_s \rightarrow 0, +\infty$

Exponential mean in problem 1

Recall that $\text{RRMSE}(\nu) = \sigma / \sqrt{\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{1}}$.

In the limit $a_s \rightarrow 0$: $\tilde{\Sigma} \rightarrow I$, where I stand for the identity matrix. Therefore $\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} \rightarrow I$ and $\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{1} \rightarrow N$, leading in turn to:

$$\text{RRMSE}(\nu) \rightarrow \sigma/\sqrt{N}$$

In the limit $a_s \rightarrow +\infty$: we note $\tilde{\Sigma} = J - \delta E$ where $J_{ij} = 1$ for all i, j , E is an invertible matrix and $\delta \rightarrow 0^+$. The inverse of $\tilde{\Sigma}$ is:

$$\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1} = -\delta^{-1}E^{-1} \left(I + \frac{\delta^{-1}JE^{-1}}{1 - \delta^{-1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1}} \right)$$

and:

$$\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{1} = -\delta^{-1} \left(\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1} + \frac{\delta^{-1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}JE^{-1}}{1 - \delta^{-1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1}} \right) = \frac{\delta^{-1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1}}{\delta^{-1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1} - 1} \rightarrow 1$$

Therefore:

$$\text{RRMSE}(\nu) \rightarrow \sigma$$

Exponential slope in problem 2

Recall that $\text{RRMSE}(\gamma) = \sigma\sqrt{\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{1}}/\sqrt{(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}})(\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{1}) - (\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}})^2}$.

In the limit $a_s \rightarrow 0$: $\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{1} \rightarrow N$, $\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}} \rightarrow 0$ and $\mathbf{x}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{x}} \rightarrow N\text{Var}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}})$, leading in turn to:

$$\text{RRMSE}(\gamma) \rightarrow \frac{\sigma}{SD(\tilde{\mathbf{x}})\sqrt{N}}$$

In the limit $a_s \rightarrow +\infty$: we use, like for exponential mean in problem 1, $\tilde{\Sigma} = J - \delta E$. Then :

$$\mathbf{1}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{x} = -\delta^{-1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{x} + \frac{-\delta^{-2}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{x}}{1 - \delta^{-1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1}} = \frac{\delta^{-1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{x}}{\delta^{-1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1} - 1} \rightarrow \frac{\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{x}}{\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1}}$$

and:

$$\mathbf{x}'\tilde{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{x} = -\delta^{-1}\mathbf{x}'E^{-1}\mathbf{x} + \frac{-\delta^{-2}\mathbf{x}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{x}}{1 - \delta^{-1}\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1}} \sim \delta^{-1} \left(\frac{(\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{x})^2}{\mathbf{1}'E^{-1}\mathbf{1}} - \mathbf{x}'E^{-1}\mathbf{x} \right)$$

Therefore:

$$\text{RRMSE}(\gamma) \rightarrow 0$$

Autocorrelation range

Here we consider the particular case of the exponential covariance model : $c(x) = e^{-x}$. Then $\frac{\partial \tilde{\Sigma}}{\partial a_s} = \frac{\sigma^2}{a_s^2} D \circ \Sigma$ where D is the distance matrix among sampling points and \circ is the Hadamard product.

When $a_s \rightarrow 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{a_s^2}{d_{\min}} e^{\frac{d_{\min}}{a_s}} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} &\rightarrow \sigma^2 R \\ e^{\frac{d_{\min}}{a_s}} (I - \sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1}) &\rightarrow R \end{aligned}$$

where d_{\min} is the smallest distance between two distinct sampling points and $R_{ij} = 1$ if $D_{ij} = d_{\min}$, 0 otherwise. Then, $\frac{a_s^2}{d_{\min}} e^{\frac{2d_{\min}}{a_s}} \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} - \sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) \rightarrow \sigma^2 R^2$ which implies in turn

$$\frac{a_s^2}{d_{\min}} e^{\frac{2d_{\min}}{a_s}} \operatorname{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) \rightarrow -\operatorname{tr}(R^2)$$

In addition,

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) &= \frac{1}{\sigma^4} \operatorname{tr} \left(\sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sigma^4} \operatorname{tr} \left((\sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} - I) \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} + \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sigma^4} \operatorname{tr} \left(\begin{array}{l} (\sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} - I) \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} (\sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} - I) \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \\ + \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \\ + (\sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} - I) \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right)^2 \end{array} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sigma^4} \operatorname{tr} \left(\begin{array}{l} (\sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} - I) \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} (\sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} - I) \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \\ + \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} (\sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} - I) \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \\ + (\sigma^2 \Sigma^{-1} - I) \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right)^2 \\ + \left(\frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right)^2 \end{array} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{a_s^4}{d_{\min}^2} e^{\frac{2d_{\min}}{a_s}} \operatorname{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) \rightarrow \operatorname{tr}(R^2)$$

which implies that :

$$\lim_{a_s \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{d_{\min}^2}{a_s^4} e^{-\frac{2d_{\min}}{a_s}} \operatorname{MSE}(a_s) \right) = \frac{2}{\operatorname{tr}(R^2)}$$

In other words, $\operatorname{MSE}(a_s)$ increases towards $+\infty$ like $a_s^4 e^{\frac{2d_{\min}}{a_s}}$ when a_s decreases towards 0.

When $a_s \rightarrow +\infty$ The assumption of exponential covariance implies that $a_s E \rightarrow D$ (see previous section for E definition), from which one obtains that $\frac{1}{a_s} E^{-1} \rightarrow D^{-1}$. Recalling that $\Sigma^{-1} = \frac{1}{\sigma^2 \mathbb{S}(E^{-1})} E^{-1} J E^{-1} - \frac{1}{\sigma^2} E^{-1}$, one obtains that:

$$\begin{aligned} a_s^2 \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} &\rightarrow \sigma^2 D \circ J = \sigma^2 D \\ \frac{1}{a_s} \Sigma^{-1} &\rightarrow \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \left(\frac{1}{\mathbb{S}(D^{-1})} D^{-1} J D^{-1} - D^{-1} \right) \end{aligned}$$

which implies:

$$\begin{aligned} a_s \operatorname{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) &\rightarrow \frac{1}{\mathbb{S}(D^{-1})} \operatorname{tr} (D^{-1} J) - N = 1 - N \\ a_s^2 \operatorname{tr} \left(\Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \Sigma^{-1} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial a_s} \right) &\rightarrow \operatorname{tr} \left(\left(\frac{1}{\mathbb{S}(D^{-1})} D^{-1} J - I \right) \left(\frac{1}{\mathbb{S}(D^{-1})} D^{-1} J - I \right) \right) = N - 1 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore :

$$\lim_{a_s \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{1}{a_s^2} \operatorname{MSE}(a_s) = \frac{2N}{N-1}$$

In other words, $\operatorname{MSE}(a_s)$ increases towards $+\infty$ like a_s^2 when a_s increases towards $+\infty$.

Relative root mean square errors

From previous results, we derive asymptotic predictions on relative root mean squared errors (RRMSE) of estimates, defined as $\operatorname{RRMSE} = \frac{\sqrt{\operatorname{MSE}(\theta)}}{\theta}$:

- $\operatorname{RRMSE}(a_s)$ increases towards $+\infty$ like $\sqrt{\frac{2}{\operatorname{tr}(R^2)}} \frac{a_s}{d_{\min}} e^{\frac{d_{\min}}{a_s}}$ as $a_s \rightarrow 0$;
- $\operatorname{RRMSE}(a_s)$ converges to $\sqrt{\frac{2N}{N-1}}$ as $a_s \rightarrow +\infty$;

3 Minimum pairwise distance

The sampled area in our study is a equilateral triangle with side length $\sqrt{3}$, which implies an area of $2 \times \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \times \frac{3}{2} = \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4}$. The number of smapling points N is kept constant. Therefore the sampling density of designs is $\lambda = \frac{4N}{3\sqrt{3}}$.

Grid design

In a regular grid design, the minimum pairwise distance corresponds d_{\min} to mesh size. A grid design made of equilateral triangles with mesh size d_{\min} reaches density $1/(d_{\min}^2 \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4})$ in the plane. Thus, using the expression of density λ associated to sampling effort N given above, one obtains that :

$$d_{\min} = \left(\frac{N}{3} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

Random design

Define $\mathcal{P}(\lambda)$ a Poisson point process with homogeneous density λ defined on the plane. Define $D_{\min}(i)$ the minimum distance between a focal point i and the other points of the design. We assume that $D_{\min}(i)$ can be well approximated by the distribution of the analogous random variable computed for a

focal point i in $\mathcal{P}(\lambda)$. Then the probability distribution function of $D_{\min}(i)$ should approximately be:

$$\mathbb{P}(D_{\min}(i) < d) \approx 1 - e^{-\pi\lambda d^2}$$

Corresponding density is :

$$f_{D_{\min}(i)}(d) \approx 2\pi\lambda d e^{-\pi\lambda d^2}$$

and approximate expectation is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[D_{\min}(i)] &\approx \int_0^{+\infty} 2\pi\lambda x^2 e^{-\pi\lambda x^2} dx \\ &= \pi\lambda \sqrt{2\pi \frac{1}{2\pi\lambda}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x^2 \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi \frac{1}{2\pi\lambda}}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\frac{1}{2\pi\lambda}}} dx \\ &= \pi\lambda \sqrt{2\pi \frac{1}{2\pi\lambda} \frac{1}{2\pi\lambda}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\lambda}} \end{aligned}$$

The minimum pairwise distance in the sampling design is $D_{\min} = \min_{i \in \{1, \dots, N\}} D_{\min}(i)$. Making the approximation that the $D_{\min}(i)$ are independent, one obtains:

$$\mathbb{P}(D_{\min} < d) \approx 1 - e^{-N\pi\lambda d^2}$$

which implies:

$$\mathbb{E}[D_{\min}] \approx \frac{1}{2\sqrt{N\lambda}} \approx \frac{27^{\frac{1}{4}}}{4N} = \frac{1}{4 \times 3^{\frac{1}{4}}} \left(\frac{N}{3}\right)^{-1}$$

$\mathbb{E}[D_{\min}]$ is therefore always lower than the d_{\min} value obtained in grid design. The relative difference between these two designs increases with sampling effort N .

Fractal design

A fractal design is obtained by applying $\log(N)/\log(3)$ times the similarities presented in main text. The k th application ($k \geq 2$) of similarities yields $d_{\min} = \rho^{k-1}(1 - \rho)\sqrt{3}$, therefore:

$$d_{\min} = (1 - \rho)\sqrt{3} \left(\frac{N}{3}\right)^{\frac{\log(\rho)}{\log(3)}}$$

Using $\rho = x\sqrt{3}/(2 + \sqrt{3})$:

$$d_{\min}(x) = \left(1 - x\sqrt{3}/(2 + \sqrt{3})\right) \sqrt{3} \left(\frac{N}{3}\right)^{-\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\log((2+\sqrt{3})/3)}{\log(3)} + \frac{\log(x)}{\log(3)}}$$

Parameter x allows arbitrarily decreasing d_{\min} for given sampling effort N . For $x = 1$, one obtains:

$$d_{\min}(1) = \left(2\sqrt{3}/(2 + \sqrt{3})\right) \left(\frac{N}{3}\right)^{-\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\log((2+\sqrt{3})/3)}{\log(3)}}$$

which is already smaller than the d_{\min} value of grid. Then $d_{\min}(x)$ decreases towards 0 as x decreases. Numerically, one obtains that $d_{\min}(x)$ becomes lower than $\mathbb{E}[D_{\min}]$ of random design when $x \approx 0.25$ for $N = 27$.

4 Shortest spanning path of fractal and grid designs

Here we derive the length of the shortest spanning path, i.e. a path that covers all sites with minimum distance, for fractal and grid designs. We denote the length of the shortest paths D^*

Grid design

We consider a grid design covering the triangular sampling area of main text, with n sites on an edge ($n = 7$ in main text). This implies that the total design has $N = n(n + 1)/2$ sampling sites. A spanning path is necessarily made of $N - 1$ straight lines. The length of each line is by definition above d_{\min} , the minimum distance between two sites in the design. Consequently, the length of the shortest spanning path is necessarily larger than $(N - 1)d_{\min}$. Reciprocally, in the case of grid design it is easy to find spanning path with a length $(N - 1)d_{\min}$. Consequently, we know that the length of shortest spanning paths is exactly $(N - 1)d_{\min}$. Using that $d_{\min} = L/(n - 1)$, and that $n = (\sqrt{1 + 8N} - 1)/2$, we obtain that:

$$D^*(N, L) = \frac{2(N - 1)L}{\sqrt{1 + 8N} - 3}$$

Fractal design

We consider a triangular fractal design covering the triangular sampling area with side length L of main text. We call n the number of scales in the design, i.e. the number of iterations of the similarities ($n = 3$ in main text).

Sampling points in the design form equilateral triangles within equilateral triangles within equilateral triangles etc. We call $d_{1,n}$, the side length of smallest equilateral triangles, $d_{2,n}$ the side length of the second smallest triangles, etc. up to $d_{n,n}$, the largest equilateral triangle of sampling points. We denote $D_{k,n}$ the smallest distance between two triangles of length side $d_{k,n}$.

Side lengths $d_{k,n}$ follow the recursive relation:

$$\begin{aligned} d_{0,n} &= 0 \\ d_{k,n} &= \rho^{n-k}(1 - \rho)L + d_{k-1,n} \end{aligned}$$

which yields the general term:

$$d_{k,n} = L\rho^{n-k}(1 - \rho^k)$$

Distance between triangles is:

$$D_{k,n} = d_{k+1,n} - 2d_{k,n} = L\rho^{n-k-1} (1 - 2\rho + \rho^{k+1})$$

Below we ask that $D_{k,n} > d_{k,n}$, which is equivalent to:

$$\rho \frac{1 - \rho^k}{1 - \rho} < \frac{1}{2}$$

which is true for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ if and only :

$$\rho < \frac{1}{3}$$

which implies, in terms of contraction parameter x :

$$x < \frac{2 + \sqrt{3}}{3\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.72$$

Under this condition, the shortest patch across the design is necessarily of form : an optimal path within a subtriangle of side length size $d_{n-1,n}$, a move to another subtriangle with length $D_{n-1,n}$, an optimal path within the new subtriangle of side length size $d_{n-1,n}$, a move to the last subtriangle with length $D_{n-1,n}$, an optimal path within the last subtriangle of side length size $d_{n-1,n}$. Calling $D^*(k, n)$ the shortest spanning path within a triangle with side length $d_{k,n}$ in the design, the following recursive relationship holds:

$$D^*(n) = 2D_{n-1,n} + 3D^*(n-1)$$

which yields the general term :

$$D^*(n) = 2 \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} 3^k D_{n-k-1,n}$$

Using that

$$D_{n-k-1,n} = L\rho^k (1 - 2\rho + \rho^{n-k})$$

one finally obtains :

$$D^*(n) = L \left(2(1 - 2\rho) \frac{1 - (3\rho)^n}{1 - 3\rho} + ((3\rho)^n - \rho^n) \right)$$